

File Name	Affinity handle	MS type	Affinity capture conditions
1410	Tb927.9.1410	MALDI-TOF	20mM HEPES, pH7.4, 250mM NaCl and 0.5% Triton
nup1_070711	NUP-1	LC-MS/MS	20mM HEPES, pH 7.4, 250mM NaCl, 0.5% Triton and 0.5% deoxy -BigCHAP
Nup2-Triton-NaCl-Citrate-3-7-12	NUP-2	LC-MS/MS	20mM HEPES, pH 7.4, 250mM Citrate, 0.5% Triton
Sam-7-20150623	Tb927.8.3950	LC-MS/MS	20mM HEPES, pH7.4, 250mM NaCl and 0.5% CHAPS